

**STUDIES ON ATANGANA-BALEANU FRACTIONAL
ORDER INTEGRO-DIFFERENTIAL SYSTEMS WITH
IMPULSIVE CONDITIONS IN BANACH SPACES**

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1 Introduction

Generalization have always been an interesting subject in mathematics. One example is the continuous gamma function which interpolates between the factorials. Another one is the fractional differential/integral operators which interpolates between integer order differential/integral operators. In fact analytic continuation of the gamma function for $x \leq 0$ plays an important role when we construct the theory of fractional order differential/integral operators from the corresponding integer order operators.

The field of fractional calculus is almost as old as calculus itself, but over the last decades the usefulness of this mathematical theory in applications as well as its merits in pure mathematics has become more and more evident. Recently a number of textbooks [8, 10, 26, 36, 41] have been published on this field dealing with various aspects in different ways. Possibly the easiest access to the idea of the non-integer differential and integral operators studied in the field of fractional calculus is given by Cauchy's well known representation of an n -fold integral as a convolution integral

$$\begin{aligned} J^n y(x) &= \int_0^x \int_0^{x_{n-1}} \cdots \int_0^{x_1} y(x_0) dx_0 \cdots dx_{n-2} dx_{n-1} \\ &= \frac{1}{(n-1)!} \int_0^x \frac{1}{(x-t)^{1-n}} y(t) dt, \quad n \in \mathbb{N}, \quad x \in \mathbb{R}_+, \end{aligned}$$

where J^n is the n -fold integral operator with $J^0 y(x) = y(x)$. Replacing the discrete factorial $(n-1)!$ with Euler's continuous gamma function $\Gamma(n)$, which satisfies $(n-1)! = \Gamma(n)$ for $n \in \mathbb{N}$, one obtains a definition of non-integer order integral, i.e.

$$J^\alpha y(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^x \frac{1}{(x-t)^{1-\alpha}} y(t) dt, \quad \alpha, x \in \mathbb{R}_+.$$

Several important aspects of fractional calculus originate from non-integer order

derivatives, which can simplest be defined as concatenation of integer order differentiation and fractional integration, i.e.

$$D^\alpha y(x) = D^n J^{n-\alpha} y(x) \quad \text{or} \quad D_*^\alpha y(x) = J^{n-\alpha} D^n y(x),$$

where n is the integer satisfying $\alpha \leq n < \alpha + 1$ and $D^n, n \in \mathbb{N}$, is the n -fold differential operator with $D^0 y(x) = y(x)$. The operator D^α is usually denoted as Riemann-Liouville differential operator, while the operator D_*^α is named Caputo differential operator. The fact that there is obviously more than one way to define non-integer order derivatives is one of the challenging and rewarding aspects of this mathematical field.

During the past three decades, the subject of fractional calculus (that is, calculus of integrals and derivatives of arbitrary order) has gained considerable popularity and importance, mainly due to its demonstrated applications in numerous diverse and widespread fields in science and engineering. For example, fractional calculus has been successfully applied to problems in system biology, physics, chemistry and biochemistry, hydrology, medicine and finance. In many cases these new fractional-order models are more adequate than the previously used integer-order models, because fractional derivatives and integrals enable the description of the memory and hereditary properties inherent in various materials and processes that are governed by anomalous diffusion. Hence, there is a growing need to find the solution behaviour of these fractional differential equations. For more details on this theory and on its applications, we suggest the reader to refer the books [26, 41] and cited references therein.

Physical and geometrical interpretations of fractional calculus are discussed by Podlubny in [41]. However the theory and applications of fractional calculus in control theory is in just initial stages of development. There has been a significant development in fractional differential equations. One can see the monographs of Baleanu et al. [13], Hilfer [23], Kilbas et al. [26], Miller and Ross [36], Zhou [46, 47] and A. Atangana [8, 10]. Recently, there has been a significant development in the existence and uniqueness of solutions of initial and boundary value problem for fractional differential equations [4, 6, 7, 9, 11, 12, 16, 17, 28, 31–33].

1.1 History of Fractional Calculus

The birthday of so-called “Fractional Calculus” is usually cited by most authors on this topic as a specific day. L’Hopital wrote a letter to Leibniz on September 30, 1695, inquiring about a special notation he had used in his writings for the n th-derivative of the linear function $f(x) = x, \frac{D^n x}{Dx^n}$. L’Hopital presented the issue to Leibniz, “What would happen if $n = \frac{1}{2}$ ”? L’Hopital’s posed the question to Leibniz, what would the result be if $n = \frac{1}{2}$?. “An apparent contradiction, from which one day beneficial conclusions will be deduced,” Leibniz responded. Fractional calculus was formed from these words.

Fractional calculus became largely a subject reserved for the greatest brains in mathematics following L’Hopital and Leibniz’s initial inquisition. Fourier, Euler, Laplace is among the numerous who tried to calculate fractional and mathematical consequences [38]. Many have found, using their own notation and methodology, definitions that fit the concept of a non-integer order integral or derivative. The Riemann-Liouville and Grunwald-Letnikov definitions are the most well-known of these definitions in the field of fractional calculus (but not yet in the rest of the world).

The greater part of the mathematical theory applicable to the study of fractional computation was developed before the turn of the century 20. Indeed, the most fascinating advances in engineering and scientific application have occurred in the last 100 years. The mathematics has in some cases had to change to meet the requirements of physical reality. Caputo reformulated the more ‘classic’ definition of the Riemann-Liouville fractional derivative in order to use integer order initial conditions to solve his fractional order differential equations [26, 41]. As recently as 1996, Kolwankar reformulated again, the Riemann-Liouville fractional derivative in order to differentiate no-where differentiable fractal functions [27].

Based on research conducted over the last 300 years, Leibniz’s response has shown to be at least half correct. It is obvious that many applications and physical manifestations of fractional calculus have been discovered, particularly in the twentieth century. These applications, as well as the mathematical background that surrounds fractional calculus, are not at all paradoxical. While the physical meaning is difficult (if not impossible) to

understand, the definitions are no more stringent than their integer order equivalents.

1.2 Special Functions

(a) Gamma function

One of the basic functions of fractional calculus is Euler's Gamma function $\Gamma(z)$, which generalizes the factorial n and allows n to take non-integer and even complex values.

Definition 1.1. [41, p.no 1]. *The Gamma function $\Gamma(z)$ is defined by the integral*

$$\Gamma(z) = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-t} t^{z-1} dt,$$

which converges in the right half of the complex plane $\Re e(z) > 0$, $z \in C$. It has the property that $\Gamma(z + 1) = z\Gamma(z)$. From this, we note that, for $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $\Gamma(n + 1) = n!$

(b) Beta function

It is more convenient to use the β function instead of a certain combination of values of the gamma function.

Definition 1.2. [41, p.no 1]. *The β function is defined by*

$$\beta(z, w) = \int_0^1 \tau^{z-1} (1 - \tau)^{w-1} d\tau, \quad \Re e(z) > 0, \quad \Re e(w) > 0, \quad z, w \in C.$$

The relationship between gamma function and beta function is given by

$$\beta(z, w) = \frac{\Gamma(z)\Gamma(w)}{\Gamma(z + w)}$$

from which it follows that $\beta(z, w) = \beta(w, z)$.

(c) Mittag-Leffler function

Aside from the gamma function, Euler discovered another significant function called the exponential function e^z , which is crucial in the theory of integer-order differential equations. For non-integer order differential equations, the Mittag-Leffler function is defined by substituting the factorial with a gamma function, which simplifies to an exponential function when the order is an integer.

Definition 1.3. [41, p.no 16]. The function $E_\alpha(z)$ defined by

$$E_\alpha(z) := \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{\Gamma(\alpha k + 1)} \quad (z \in C, \operatorname{Re}(\alpha) > 0), \quad (1.2.1)$$

was introduced by Mittag-Leffler and is, therefore, known as the Mittag-Leffler function.

The Mittag-Leffler function $E_{\alpha,\beta}(z)$, generalizing the one in (1.2.1), is defined by

$$E_{\alpha,\beta}(z) := \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{\Gamma(\alpha k + \beta)} \quad (z, \beta \in C, \operatorname{Re}(\alpha) > 0). \quad (1.2.2)$$

This function is some times called a Mittag-Leffler type function.

In particular, when $\alpha = 1$ and $\alpha = 2$, we have from (1.2.1)

$$\begin{aligned} E_1(z) &= e^z, \\ E_2(z) &= \cosh(\sqrt{z}). \end{aligned}$$

When $\beta = 1$, $E_{\alpha,\beta}(z)$ coincides with the Mittag-Leffler function (1.2.1), namely

$$E_{\alpha,1}(z) = E_\alpha(z) \quad (z \in C, \operatorname{Re}(\alpha) > 0).$$

The particular cases of (1.2.2) are given by

$$E_{1,2}(z) = \frac{e^{z-1}}{z}, \quad E_{2,2}(z) = \frac{\sin h(\sqrt{z})}{\sqrt{(z)}}.$$

In fractional calculus, Mittag-Leffler functions perform a unique role. When fractional calculus approaches are used to solve specific issues, they frequently occur. Because the basic solution of a fractional linear differential equation with constant coefficients is stated in terms of Mittag-Leffler type functions, this is the case.

1.3 Existence

In fact fractional differential equations are considered as an alternative model to nonlinear differential equations [15]. It draws a great application in nonlinear oscillations of earthquakes, many physical phenomena such as seepage flow in porous media and in fluid dynamic traffic models. Fractional derivative can eliminate the deficiency of

continuum traffic flow. The most important advantage of using fractional differential equations in these and other applications [21] is their nonlocal property. It is well known that the integer order differential operator is a local operator but the fractional order differential operator is non-local. This means that the next state of a system depends not only upon its current state but also upon all of its historical states. This is probably the most relevant feature for making this fractional tool useful from an applied standpoint and interesting from a mathematical standpoint and in turn led to the sustained study of theory of fractional differential equations [26].

The existence of solutions for fractional integro-differential equations via resolvent operator investigated in [2] and the existence of fractional neutral functional differential equations are discussed in [3] whereas the existence of solutions of fractional differential equations by using fixed point techniques have been discussed by several authors [4, 6, 7, 9, 11, 12, 16, 17, 28, 31–33, 35, 37, 39].

Fractional calculus, which is as old as the traditional calculus and generalization of it. It is a brilliant medium to analyze the world around us via the fields of pure and applied mathematics [8, 10, 11]. Due to its long - term memory retaining and hereditary property fractional calculus receiving a lot of attention from diverse fields of researchers all around the world. By the continuous dedicated contribution of mathematicians such as Caputo, Riemann, Liouville, and so forth, the fractional calculus becomes the potential new field of research with lots of new ideas everyday which attracts the young researchers towards this field. In [5, 24], the authors developed the fractional differential operator for a function and several generalizations of such operators concerned with some fractional derivatives as such Caputo, Caputo-katugampola and Atangana-Baleanu. These operators are helpful in solving many problems in population growth and other models.

The Liouville - Caputo fractional derivative kernel which has memory effects based on the power law having singularity in its origin. Here, power law is not enough to model all the physical problems. Therefore, Liouville - Caputo's definition for fractional derivatives is less effective. In [16], the new notion of fractional derivative having no singular kernel is used. In [17], authors have investigated the Caputo-Fabrizio fractional operator and it

possesses a regular kernel which was the special feature about it. To show the significance of Caputo-Fabrizio operator the authors developed several numerical simulations using the Laplace transform algorithm; more works related with this fractional derivative are given in [8–11]. In [8–10], Atangana and Baleanu proposed a new kernel on the basis of the Mittag-Leffler function; the proposed kernel is nonlocal and nonsingular. Interesting observation is that their fractional integral is the fractional average of the Riemann-Liouville fractional integral of the given function and the function itself. The fractional derivatives proposed by Atangana and Baleanu are at the same time filters and fractional derivatives.

The sudden change experienced by the state of existence at particular moments happens generally in modelling the real-life problems which is almost similar to the graphs which is not always a straight line having some ups and downs at particular momentum. Likewise, the mathematical modelling of such natural processes was framed by instantaneous impulsive differential equations. The processes with such features occur in almost every field such as physics, chemistry, biology, economics and dynamics. For further references, one can go through the monographs by Benchohra et al. [14], Lakshmikantham et al. [29], and the papers of Mallika Arjunan et al. [34], Li and Liu [30] for more comments and citations. In the last few decades, investigating the theory of instantaneous impulsive evolution equations in Banach space has become an important topic of research due to its wide applicability in diverse fields. For more references, we refer [14, 34].

The simulation process described by instantaneous impulsive ordinary and partial differential equations captures the evolution process and its small perturbations with much perfection. The perturbation occurs discretely at random moments and remains active for some finite time duration and it is negligible when compared to the duration of the total process. In brief, the problems with abrupt and instantaneous changes were framed by impulsive ordinary and partial differential equations with instantaneous impulses. However, instantaneous impulses are not sufficient to explain the evolution process in all cases. For example, pharmacotherapy. In [22], Hernandez and O' Regan considered the hemodynamic equilibrium for the simple understanding of impulse of non-instantaneous nature. The hemodynamic equilibrium is the introduction of drugs in the blood and consequently followed by the absorption of drugs by the body. In this process, the

effectiveness of a drug remains in an active state for some time of finite duration. Here, it is a continuous and gradual process different from instantaneous process is known to be non-instantaneous impulsive in nature. The partial differential equations with non-instantaneous impulses have been used widely to describe realistic models with accuracy.

In [18, 22, 37], several authors have started showing importance towards the non-linear equations having non-instantaneous impulses. In [40], Pierre et al. investigated semi-linear abstract differential equations with non-instantaneous impulses and used the semigroup theory to obtain the existence results of mild solutions for the same system. Colao et al. [19] obtained the existence of solutions for a second-order differential equation with non-instantaneous impulses and delay on an unbounded interval by establish a compactness criterion in a certain class of functions. In [43], Yu and Wang used the semigroup theory and fixed point methods to study the solutions of periodic boundary value problems for non-linear cases with non-instantaneous impulses on Banach spaces. In [45], Wang and Li studied the non-linear ordinary differential equation with non-instantaneous impulses for periodic boundary value problems. For further reference, we refer [1, 25, 35, 42, 44].

In recent times, several authors have started showing more interest towards non-linear fractional differential equations with non-instantaneous equations, we refer [1, 18, 20, 25, 35, 42]. In [20], the authors have studied the fractional functional integro-differential equations with non-instantaneous impulses and discussed the existence, uniqueness and continuous dependence of mild solutions. In [35], Meeraj et al. investigated the fractional non-instantaneous impulsive integro-differential equations with nonlocal conditions and examined the existence of a solution using non-compact semigroup theory and fixed point theorem. In [25], Kumar et al. furnished the sufficient conditions for the existence results of mild solutions for Atangana - Baleanu non-instantaneous impulse fractional differential system. Recently, Mallika Arjunan et al. [31, 32] analyzed the existence results of various fractional differential systems through Atangana-Baleanu derivative under suitable fixed point theorem.

Motivated by the above facts, in this thesis, we have been studied the existence and controllability results for different types of Atangana-Baleanu fractional differential and integro-differential systems (equations/inclusions) with impulsive conditions

(instantaneous/non-instantaneous) in Banach spaces under suitable fixed point theorem.

In the light of the above, the author has obtained some significant generalizations on the following topics:

2 Existence of a solution for a fractional integro-differential equation with non-instantaneous impulses and Mittag-Leffler kernel

In this chapter, firstly, we discuss the existence results for Atangana-Baleanu fractional differential equation with non-instantaneous impulses of the model

$$\mathcal{D}_{ABC}^{\vartheta} w(\alpha) = \mathcal{Q}w(\alpha) + \mathcal{F}(\alpha, w(\alpha)), \quad \alpha \in \cup_{\ell=0}^m (s_{\ell}, \alpha_{\ell+1}] \quad (2.1.1)$$

$$w(\alpha) = I_{\ell}(w(\alpha_{\ell})) + \kappa_{\ell}(\alpha, w(\alpha)), \quad \alpha \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m (\alpha_{\ell}, s_{\ell}] \quad (2.1.2)$$

$$w(0) = w_0 \in E, \quad (2.1.3)$$

where $J = [0, \tau], \tau > 0$ is the operational interval, $\vartheta \in (0, 1)$, $\mathcal{Q} : D(\mathcal{Q}) \subset E \rightarrow E$ is the infinitesimal generator of an ϑ -resolvent family $\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_{\vartheta}(\alpha)_{\alpha \geq 0}$, the solution operator $\mathcal{B}_{\vartheta}(\alpha)_{\alpha \geq 0}$ is described on a complex Banach space E , $\mathcal{D}_{ABC}^{\vartheta}$ is the Atangana-Baleanu-Caputo derivative, $0 = \alpha_0 = s_0 < \alpha_1 \leq s_1 < \alpha_2 \leq s_2 < \dots < \alpha_m \leq s_m < \alpha_{m+1} = \tau$; $\mathcal{F} : \cup_{\ell=0}^m (s_{\ell}, \alpha_{\ell+1}] \times E \rightarrow E$ is a given function which satisfies assumptions to be specified later on. We consider the non-instantaneous impulsive functions $\kappa_{\ell} : (\alpha_{\ell}, s_{\ell}] \times E \rightarrow E$, $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$, and $I_{\ell} : E \rightarrow E$, $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$ and $w_0 \in E$.

The impulses in system (2.1.1)-(2.1.3) begin rapidly at the points α_{ℓ} and their process continues on the interval $[\alpha_{\ell}, s_{\ell}]$. To be exact, the function w takes an instantaneous impulse at α_{ℓ} and applies various conditions in the two sub-intervals $(\alpha_{\ell}, s_{\ell}]$ and $(s_{\ell}, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$ of the interval $(\alpha_{\ell}, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$. The function w is continuous at the point s_{ℓ} . The phrase $I_{\ell}(w(\alpha_{\ell}))$ denotes that the impulses are frequently linked to the value of $w(\alpha_{\ell}) = w(\alpha_{\ell}^-)$.

We observe that if $\alpha_{\ell} = s_{\ell}$ and (2.1.2) takes the structure of $\Delta w(\alpha_{\ell}) = I_{\ell}(w(\alpha_{\ell})) = w(\alpha_{\ell}^+) - w(\alpha_{\ell}^-)$ with $w(\alpha_{\ell}^+) = \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0^+} w(\alpha_{\ell} + \epsilon)$, $w(\alpha_{\ell}^-) = \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0^-} w(\alpha_{\ell} + \epsilon)$ expressing the right and left limits of $w(\alpha)$ at $\alpha = \alpha_{\ell}$.

We also establish the existence and uniqueness of mild solutions for the nonlocal

Cauchy problem

$$\mathcal{D}_{ABC}^{\vartheta} w(\alpha) = \mathcal{Q}w(\alpha) + \mathcal{F}(\alpha, w(\alpha)), \quad \alpha \in \cup_{\ell=0}^m (s_{\ell}, \alpha_{\ell+1}] \quad (2.1.4)$$

$$w(\alpha) = I_{\ell}(w(\alpha_{\ell})) + \kappa_{\ell}(\alpha, w(\alpha)), \quad \alpha \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m (\alpha_{\ell}, s_{\ell}] \quad (2.1.5)$$

$$w(0) = w_0 - g(w) \in E, \quad (2.1.6)$$

where $\mathcal{D}_{ABC}^{\vartheta}$, \mathcal{Q} , \mathcal{F} , I and κ are same as described in system (2.1.1)-(2.1.3) and g is an appropriate given function; this frames a nonlocal Cauchy problem.

Further, in this chapter, we also discuss the existence and uniqueness of mild solutions of Atangana-Baleanu fractional integro-differential equations of the form

$$\mathcal{D}_{ABC}^{\vartheta} w(\alpha) = \mathcal{Q}w(\alpha) + \mathcal{F}\left(\alpha, w(\alpha), \int_0^{\alpha} k(\alpha, s, w(s))ds\right), \quad \alpha \in \cup_{\ell=0}^m (s_{\ell}, \alpha_{\ell+1}] \quad (2.1.7)$$

$$w(\alpha) = \kappa_{\ell}(\alpha, w(\alpha_{\ell}^{-})), \quad \alpha \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m (\alpha_{\ell}, s_{\ell}] \quad (2.1.8)$$

$$w(0) = w_0 \in E, \quad (2.1.9)$$

where $\mathcal{D}_{ABC}^{\vartheta}$ is the Atangana-Baleanu-Caputo derivative of order ϑ , where $0 < \vartheta < 1$. $\mathcal{Q} : D(\mathcal{Q}) \subseteq E \rightarrow E$ is the infinitesimal generator of ϑ -resolvent operator $\{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_{\vartheta}(\alpha)\}_{\alpha \geq 0}$, $\{\mathcal{B}_{\vartheta}(\alpha)\}_{\alpha \geq 0}$ is the solution operator on a complex Banach space $(E, \|\cdot\|)$, $\mathcal{J} = [0, \tau]$, $\tau > 0$ is a constant, $0 = \alpha_0 < \alpha_1 < \alpha_2 < \dots < \alpha_m < \alpha_{m+1} = \tau$, $s_0 = 0$; $w(\alpha_{\ell}^{+}) = \kappa_{\ell}(\alpha_{\ell}, w(\alpha_{\ell}^{-}))$, where the symbols $w(\alpha_{\ell}^{+}) := \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0^{+}} w(\alpha_{\ell} + \epsilon)$ and $w(\alpha_{\ell}^{-}) := \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0^{-}} w(\alpha_{\ell} + \epsilon)$ represent the right and the left limits of $w(\alpha)$ at $\alpha = \alpha_{\ell}$ respectively and $s_{\ell} \in (\alpha_{\ell}, \alpha_{\ell+1})$ for each $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$; $\mathcal{F} : \cup_{\ell=0}^m (s_{\ell}, \alpha_{\ell+1}] \times E \times E \rightarrow E$; $k : \Delta \times E \rightarrow E$, where $\Delta = \{(w, s) : 0 \leq s \leq w \leq \tau\}$ are given function which satisfies assumptions to be specified later on. $\kappa_{\ell} : (\alpha_{\ell}, s_{\ell}] \times E \rightarrow E$ are non-instantaneous impulsive functions for each $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$ and $w_0 \in E$. For our convenience, we denote $E_1 w(\alpha) = \int_0^{\alpha} k(\alpha, s, w(s))ds$.

The results are obtained by using the Banach and Krasnoselskii's fixed point theorem.

3 On a new class of Atangana-Baleanu fractional Volterra-Fredholm integro-differential inclusions with non-instantaneous impulses

In this chapter, we analyze the existence of mild solutions of Atangana-Baleanu fractional Volterra-Fredholm integro-differential inclusion with non-instantaneous

impulses of the form

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}_{ABC}^{\vartheta} w(\alpha) &\in \mathcal{Q}w(\alpha) + \mathcal{F} \left(\alpha, w(\alpha), \int_0^{\alpha} \chi(\alpha, s, w(s)) ds, \int_0^{\tau} \tilde{\chi}(\alpha, s, w(s)) ds \right), \\ \alpha &\in \cup_{\ell=0}^m (s_{\ell}, \alpha_{\ell+1}] \\ w(\alpha) &= I_{\ell}(w(\alpha_{\ell})) + \kappa_{\ell}(\alpha, w(\alpha)), \quad \alpha \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m (\alpha_{\ell}, s_{\ell}] \\ w(0) &= w_0 \in E, \end{aligned} \tag{3.1.1}$$

where $\mathcal{D}_{ABC}^{\vartheta}$ is the Atangana-Baleanu-Caputo derivative of order $\vartheta \in (0, 1)$ with the lower limit zero. $\mathcal{Q} : D(\mathcal{Q}) \subseteq E \rightarrow E$ is the infinitesimal generator of ϑ -resolvent operator $\{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_{\vartheta}(\alpha)\}_{\alpha \geq 0}, \{\mathcal{B}_{\vartheta}(\alpha)\}_{\alpha \geq 0}$ is the solution operator on a complex Banach space $(E, \|\cdot\|)$, $\mathcal{J} = [0, \tau], \tau > 0$ is a constant, $0 = \alpha_0 = s_0 < \alpha_1 \leq s_1 < \alpha_2 \leq s_2 < \dots < \alpha_m \leq s_m < \alpha_{m+1} = \tau$, are pre-fixed numbers. $\mathcal{F} : \cup_{\ell=0}^m (s_{\ell}, \alpha_{\ell+1}] \times E^3 \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(E)$ is a set valued map, $\chi, \tilde{\chi} : \Delta \times E \rightarrow E$, where $\Delta = \{(\alpha, s) : 0 \leq s \leq \alpha \leq \tau\}$ are given functions which fulfills certain conditions to be defined later on. For each $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m, \kappa_{\ell} : (\alpha_{\ell}, s_{\ell}] \times E \rightarrow E$ are non-instantaneous impulsive functions; $I_{\ell} : E \rightarrow E$ for $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$ and $w_0 \in E$. For our convenience, we denote $E_1 w(\alpha) = \int_0^{\alpha} \chi(\alpha, s, w(s)) ds$ and $E_2 w(\alpha) = \int_0^{\tau} \tilde{\chi}(\alpha, s, w(s)) ds$.

The impulses in system (3.1.1) begin rapidly at the points α_{ℓ} and their process continues on the interval $[\alpha_{\ell}, s_{\ell}]$. To be exact, the function w takes an instantaneous impulse at α_{ℓ} and applies various conditions in the two sub-intervals $(\alpha_{\ell}, s_{\ell}]$ and $(s_{\ell}, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$ of the interval $(\alpha_{\ell}, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$. At the point s_{ℓ} , the function w is continuous. The term $I_{\ell}(w(\alpha_{\ell}))$ implies that the impulses are often connected to the value of $w(\alpha_{\ell}) = w(\alpha_{\ell}^-)$.

We notice that if $\alpha_{\ell} = s_{\ell}$ and the second equation of (3.1.1) comes as a form of $\Delta w(\alpha_{\ell}) = I_{\ell}(w(\alpha_{\ell})) = w(\alpha_{\ell}^+) - w(\alpha_{\ell}^-)$ with $w(\alpha_{\ell}^+) = \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0^+} w(\alpha_{\ell} + \epsilon), w(\alpha_{\ell}^-) = \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0^-} w(\alpha_{\ell} + \epsilon)$ describing the right and left limits of $w(\alpha)$ at $\alpha = \alpha_{\ell}$.

The results are obtained by using the Martelli's fixed point theorem.

4 Existence results for Atangana-Baleanu fractional neutral integro-differential systems with infinite delay through sectorial operators

In this chapter, firstly, we examine the existence of mild solutions of Atangana-Baleanu fractional semi-linear integro-differential equation with infinite delay of the form

$$\mathcal{D}_{ABC}^{\vartheta} w(\alpha) = \mathcal{Q}w(\alpha) + \mathcal{F} \left(\alpha, w_{\alpha}, \int_0^{\alpha} k(\alpha, s, w_s) ds \right), \quad \alpha \in \mathcal{J} = [0, \tau] \quad (4.1.1)$$

$$w(\alpha) = \varphi(\alpha) \in \mathcal{B}, \quad (4.1.2)$$

where $\mathcal{D}_{ABC}^{\vartheta}$ is the Atangana-Baleanu-Caputo (ABC) derivative of order ϑ , where $0 < \vartheta < 1$. $\mathcal{Q} : D(\mathcal{Q}) \subseteq E \rightarrow E$ is the infinitesimal generator of ϑ -resolvent operator $\{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_{\vartheta}(\alpha)\}_{\alpha \geq 0}, \{\mathcal{B}_{\vartheta}(\alpha)\}_{\alpha \geq 0}$ is the solution operator on a complex Banach space $(E, \|\cdot\|)$, $\mathcal{J} = [0, \tau], \tau > 0$ is a constant; $\mathcal{F} : \mathcal{J} \times \mathcal{B} \times E \rightarrow E; k : \Delta \times \mathcal{B} \rightarrow E$, where $\Delta = \{(\alpha, s) : 0 \leq s \leq \alpha \leq \tau\}$ are given functions which ensures assertions to be defined subsequently. For our convenience, we label $E_1 w_s = \int_0^{\alpha} k(\alpha, s, w_s) ds$.

For any function w defined on $(-\infty, +\infty)$ and any $\alpha \geq 0$, we denote w_{α} the element of \mathcal{B} defined by $w_{\alpha}(\theta) = w(\alpha + \theta), \theta \in (-\infty, 0]$ up to the present time α . We assume that the histories w_{α} belong to some abstract phase space \mathcal{B} axioms.

Further, in this chapter, we also discuss the existence results for Atangana-Baleanu fractional semi-linear neutral integro-differential equation of the form

$$\mathcal{D}_{ABC}^{\vartheta} [w(\alpha) - \mathcal{G}(\alpha, w_{\alpha})] = \mathcal{Q}w(\alpha) + \mathcal{F} \left(\alpha, w_{\alpha}, \int_0^{\alpha} k(\alpha, s, w_s) ds \right), \quad (4.1.3)$$

$$w(\alpha) = \varphi(\alpha) \in \mathcal{B}, \quad (4.1.4)$$

where $\alpha \in \mathcal{J} = [0, \tau]$ and $\mathcal{G} : \mathcal{J} \times \mathcal{B} \rightarrow E$ is a continuous function and other functions are same as defined in system (4.1.1)-(4.1.2).

The results are obtained by using Banach, Leray-Schauder and Krasnoselskii-Schaefer's fixed point theorem.

5 A new existence results on fractional differential inclusions with state-dependent delay and Mittag-Leffler kernel in Banach space

In this chapter, we establish the existence of mild solutions of Atangana-Baleanu fractional functional differential inclusion with state-dependent delay of the form

$$\mathcal{D}_{ABC}^\vartheta p(\alpha) \in Ap(\alpha) + \mathcal{F}(\alpha, p_{\sigma(\alpha, p_\alpha)}), \quad \alpha \in [0, \tau] \quad (5.1.1)$$

$$p(\alpha) = \varphi(\alpha) \in \mathcal{B}, \quad (5.1.2)$$

where $\tau > 0, \vartheta \in (0, 1)$, $A : D(A) \subset E \rightarrow E$ is the infinitesimal generator of an ϑ -resolvent family $\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha)_{\alpha \geq 0}$, the solution operator $\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)_{\alpha \geq 0}$ is described on a complex Banach space E , $\mathcal{D}_{ABC}^\vartheta$ is the Atangana-Baleanu-Caputo derivative, \mathcal{F} is a set-valued map and $\sigma : [0, \tau] \times \mathcal{B} \rightarrow (-\infty, \tau]$ are given functions that satisfy a later-specified assumption.

We assume that $p_\alpha : (-\infty, 0] \rightarrow E, p_\alpha(x) = p(\alpha + x), x \leq 0$, belongs to an abstract phase space \mathcal{B} axioms.

The results are obtained by using the contractive and condensing maps.

6 Non-instantaneous impulsive fractional-order delay differential systems with Mittag-Leffler kernel

In this chapter, we address the existence findings for a class of fractional functional differential equation with non-instantaneous impulses and Mittag-Leffler kernel of the form

$$\mathcal{D}_{ABC}^\vartheta p(\alpha) = Ap(\alpha) + \mathcal{F}(\alpha, p_\alpha), \quad \cup_{\ell=0}^m (s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}] \quad (6.1.1)$$

$$p(\alpha) = \kappa_\ell(\alpha, p_\alpha), \quad \alpha \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell] \quad (6.1.2)$$

$$p(\alpha) = \varphi(\alpha) \in \mathcal{B}, \quad (6.1.3)$$

where $J = [0, \tau], \tau > 0$ is the operational interval, $\vartheta \in (0, 1)$, $A : D(A) \subset E \rightarrow E$ is the infinitesimal generator of an ϑ -resolvent family $\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha)_{\alpha \geq 0}$, the solution operator $\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)_{\alpha \geq 0}$ is described on a complex Banach space E , $\mathcal{D}_{ABC}^\vartheta$ is the Atangana-Baleanu-Caputo derivative, $0 < \alpha_1 < \alpha_2 < \dots < \alpha_m < \alpha_{m+1} = \tau, s_0 = 0$ and $s_\ell \in (\alpha_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1})$ for each $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$; $\mathcal{F} : \cup_{\ell=0}^m (s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}] \times \mathcal{B} \rightarrow E$ is a stated function that meets later-specified assumptions. We consider the non-instantaneous impulsive functions $\kappa_\ell : (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell] \times \mathcal{B} \rightarrow E, \ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$ and $\varphi \in \mathcal{B}$.

We assume that $p_\alpha : (-\infty, 0] \rightarrow E, p_\alpha(x) = p(\alpha + x), x \leq 0$, belongs to an abstract phase space \mathcal{B} axioms.

The results are obtained by using the Monch's fixed point theorem.

7 Existence and controllability of fractional integro-differential equation with infinite delay and impulsive effects

In this chapter, we establish the existence and controllability of mild solutions for an impulsive Atangana-Baleanu fractional functional differential system with infinite delay of the model

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}_{ABC}^{\vartheta} p(\alpha) &= Ap(\alpha) + f(\alpha, p_{\alpha}, Np(\alpha)), \quad \alpha \in [0, \tau], \alpha \neq \alpha_{\ell}, \ell = 1, 2, \dots, q, \\ \Delta p(\alpha_{\ell}) &= I_{\ell}(p(\alpha_{\ell}^{-})), \quad \ell = 1, 2, \dots, q, \\ p(\alpha) &= \varphi(\alpha), \quad \varphi(\alpha) \in \mathfrak{C}_h, \end{aligned} \quad (7.1.1)$$

and the corresponding controllability model

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}_{ABC}^{\vartheta} p(\alpha) &= Ap(\alpha) + f(\alpha, p_{\alpha}, Np(\alpha)) + (G\nu)(\alpha), \quad \alpha \in [0, \tau], \alpha \neq \alpha_{\ell}, \\ \Delta p(\alpha_{\ell}) &= I_{\ell}(p(\alpha_{\ell}^{-})), \quad \ell = 1, 2, \dots, q, \\ p(\alpha) &= \varphi(\alpha), \quad \varphi(\alpha) \in \mathfrak{C}_h, \end{aligned} \quad (7.1.2)$$

where $\tau > 0, \vartheta \in (0, 1)$, $A : D(A) \subset E \rightarrow E$ is the infinitesimal generator of an ϑ -resolvent family $\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_{\vartheta}(\alpha)_{\alpha \geq 0}$, the solution operator $\mathcal{B}_{\vartheta}(\alpha)_{\alpha \geq 0}$ is described on a complex Banach space E , $\mathcal{D}_{ABC}^{\vartheta}$ is the Atangana-Baleanu-Caputo derivative, $f : [0, \tau] \times \mathfrak{C}_h \times E \rightarrow E$ is a given function; G is a bounded linear operator from a Banach space $\widehat{\mathcal{B}}$ into E ; the control function $\nu(\cdot) \in L^2([0, \tau], \widehat{\mathcal{B}})$, a Banach space of admissible control function and \mathfrak{C}_h is a phase space axioms. Here, $0 = \alpha_0 < \alpha_1 < \dots < \alpha_q < \alpha_{q+1} = \tau$, $I_{\ell} \in \mathcal{C}(E, E)$, $(\ell = 1, 2, \dots, q)$, are bounded functions, $\Delta p(\alpha_{\ell}) = p(\alpha_{\ell}^+) - p(\alpha_{\ell}^-)$, $p(\alpha_{\ell}^+) = \lim_{e \rightarrow 0} p(\alpha_{\ell} + e)$ and $p(\alpha_{\ell}^-) = \lim_{e \rightarrow 0} p(\alpha_{\ell} - e)$ represent the right and left limits of $p(\alpha)$ at $\alpha = \alpha_{\ell}$, respectively.

We assume that $p_{\alpha} : (-\infty, 0] \rightarrow E, p_{\alpha}(x) = p(\alpha + x)$, $x \leq 0$, belongs to an abstract phase space \mathfrak{C}_h . The expression $Np(\alpha)$ is defined by $Np(\alpha) = \int_0^{\alpha} \mathcal{B}(\alpha, s)p(s)ds$, where $\mathcal{B} \in \mathcal{C}(K, \mathbb{R}^+)$ and $K = \{(\alpha, s) \in \mathbb{R}^2 : 0 \leq s \leq \alpha \leq \tau\}$.

The results are obtained by using the Banach, Krasnoselskii's and Schaefer's fixed point theorem.

This synopsis presents a brief discussion of the various results obtained by the author under the above topics. Most of the works to be incorporated in the proposed thesis has been published in the following journals:

- (1) On a new class of Atangana-Baleanu fractional Volterra-Fredholm integro-differential inclusions with non-instantaneous impulses, *Chaos, Solitons and Fractals*, 148(2021), 111075.
- (2) Existence results for Atangana-Baleanu fractional neutral integro-differential systems with infinite delay through sectorial operators, *Chaos, Solitons and Fractals*, 149(2021), 111042.
- (3) Existence results for Atangana-Baleanu fractional integro-differential systems with non-instantaneous impulses, *Nonlinear Studies*, 28(3)(2021), 865–877.
- (4) Non-instantaneous impulsive fractional-order delay differential systems with Mittag-Leffler kernel, *AIMS Mathematics*, Communicated, 2021.
- (5) Existence of a solution for a fractional delay differential equation with non-instantaneous impulses and Mittag-Leffler kernel, *Journal of Applied Mathematics and Computing*, Communicated, 2021.
- (6) Existence and controllability of fractional integro-differential equation with infinite delay and impulsive effects, *Chaos, Solitons and Fractals*, Communicated, 2021.
- (7) A new existence results on fractional differential inclusions with state-dependent delay and Mittag-Leffler kernel in Banach space, *Analele Universitatii "Ovidius" Constanta - Seria Matematica*, Communicated, 2021.

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